

TGB Osborn Vegetation Reserve

Background to the collection in TERN V3

1 Introduction

In the mid-1920's Professor Theodore George Bentley Osborn, Professor of Botany in the University of Adelaide, put forward strong scientific arguments concerning the lack of knowledge of the ecology of arid zone vegetation, and the effect of grazing on it (Osborn, 1925). In 1925 negotiations proceeded between the University of Adelaide and Messrs Hamilton Wilcox Ltd to secure a parcel of land for the purposes of research on Koonamore Station, a sheep-grazing property approximately 400 km north-east of Adelaide (Figure 1). The station lies in the semi-arid rangelands of South Australia. The vegetation of the station was extensively described by Carrodus *et al.* (1965).

A parcel of land of around 390ha was identified in South Lake Paddock and fenced to exclude rabbits and other stock, and Mr Wilcox, one of the directors, had a three-roomed house (Bindy-I) erected to serve as a field laboratory (Osborn, 1925). The area was originally referred to as the Arid Region Flora Reserve but later was named the TGB Osborn Vegetation Reserve after its founder. For simplicity it is commonly referred to as the Koonamore Vegetation Reserve. There have been some unwanted animal incursions over the years, but these have been rare. In 1931, for example, rabbits were able to enter due to fence damage (Hall *et al.*, 1964). Kangaroos and emus are not fully excluded.

At the time of creation of the reserve, the vegetation within it was much reduced by stock activity (Hall *et al.*, 1964). The substrate consists of low-lying sand dunes with hard loamy soils on the intervening flats (Osborn *et al.*, 1935). The three dominant soil types found on the reserve are sand and sandy loam, silt flats, and hard loamy soils with calcrete. These were representative of the main soil types of the arid plains of South Australia (Osborn *et al.*, 1935). Rainfall is low and highly variable with an annual average of 218mm with a standard deviation of 125mm (Lawley *et al.*, 2013).

Figure 1: Location of Koonamore Station in South Australia, in which the TGB Osborn Vegetation Reserve is situated (map adapted from Figure 1, Hall *et al.* 1964).

The overstorey of the site is classified as low open woodland. The sand dunes carry *Acacia aneura* (mulga), *A. burkittii* and various *Eremophila* spp., the sand plain a dense stand of *Casuarina pauper* (blackoak, belah), and the harder loam soils a mixed community of *Myoporum platycarpum* (false sandalwood) and *Alectryon oleifolius* (bullock bush, rosewood). Understorey shrubs, which also form low chenopod shrubland communities in some areas, include *Atriplex vesicaria* (bladder saltbush), *A. stipitata* and *Maireana sedifolia* (bluebush) (Sinclair, 2005). Numerous other chenopodiaceous shrubs also occur, and grass and ephemeral herb cover varies with the seasons. Several species of *Senna*, *Eremophila* and other shrubs also occur.

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2 The monitoring program

As is clear from the objectives stated by TGB Osborn, the reserve was to provide the basis for systematic measurements of the now-protected vegetation. Osborn and his team (including Prof. J.G. Wood and Mr Terry Paltridge) set up a series of quadrats (square plots) and photopoints within the reserve. A series of transects was later added (Figure 2). All of the foregoing were permanently marked, and observations on species occurrence (presence and abundance) and physical measurements of the plants were made repeatedly, but at varying intervals.

Figure 2: Sketch map of the type and distribution of measurements at the TGB Osborn Vegetation Reserve. Not all photopoint positions are shown, and the scale is approximate. Bindy-I is the field laboratory. The map is derived from Osborn *et al.*, 1935, Hall *et al.*, 1964, Crisp, unpublished map, 1972, lists of georeferences for many of the locations, and Google maps.

Reserve coordinates: NE corner: -32.10834° 139.35187°, SE corner: -32.12459° 139.35141°, SW corner: -32.12401° 139.32794°, NW corner: -32.10767° 139.32858°.

Observations from these monitoring sites have been repeated over the century of existence of the reserve, now making it one of the longest-measured such sites in the world (Sinclair, 2005). There have been periodic major temporal reviews of the vegetation data collected at the site, such as by Hall *et al.*, 1964, Sinclair, 2005, and Lawley *et al.*, 2013, and many shorter-term or specific studies (e.g. of a particular species or attribute such as lichens, invertebrates or dead wood). A full bibliography of published articles and theses is available in the TERN Data Discovery Portal ([TDDP](#)) resource material.

3 The data available in the TERN Data Discovery Portal (TDDP)

Records of the different measurements and observations of the reserve obtained from the original recording sheets at the University of Adelaide were entered into AEKOS (a TERN facility) in 2008–2014 by [Dr Russ Sinclair](#) (who died in 2023). The data currently available has been cleaned and revised by [Dr Alison Specht](#) with the assistance of TERN staff to ensure the data are FAIR compliant (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable: Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016) (Table 1). Each category of data has at least one spreadsheet (.csv), a data dictionary (.csv) for each spreadsheet, and a metadata file explaining the content of the file(s). With the exception of undocumented photographs, no data other than those supplied by Dr Sinclair in 2014 are available digitally (February 2026).

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Table 1: The data sets available through the [TDDP](#), arranged according to year of commencement.

Data category	Brief description	date range
Vegetation quadrats	Data from repeat surveys of abundance and physical attributes of species within a suite of fixed plots (quadrats) within the Reserve: 5 large (100x100m), 1x400m ² , 8x100m ² plots, and 4x1m ² plots, and 13 'fire' quadrats	1926-2014
Photopoints	Two forms of data are available (a) images taken from fixed points, and (b) observations associated with the images. The date range is variable but generally images start in the mid 1920s and extend until 2008, while measurements run from the mid-1920s until 1988. The two data types are linked. The nearly 6,000 images are housed in TERN Ecolimages .	1907-2008
Cassia corner	Data on Cassia (<i>Senna</i> spp.) abundance in a 1750 m ² rectangle on 26 occasions.	1940-2014
Myoporum individuals	Data of the physical attributes of 25 individuals of <i>Myoporum platycarpum</i> on 21 occasions.	1955-2011
Kangaroo scats	Data on kangaroo activity as evidenced by scat occurrence on 40 occasions both inside and outside the Reserve. Data on occasional incursions by sheep and goats is included.	1968-2022
Rabbit warren numbers	Data from surveys of the Reserve for rabbit activity are available for 56 occasions using the number of rabbit warrens (one warren indicated by 4 entrances) as evidence of rabbit presence.	1977-2014
Saltbush transects	Data of <i>Senna</i> spp. occurrence between 1930 and 2008 from four paired transects on four occasions. Photographs are associated with these transects and are available through the photopoint data set.	1989-2014
Senna populations	Data from 10 occasions on the effect of three treatments (plus a control) to protect <i>Senna</i> seedlings from grazing.	1997-2008

In addition the following files are supplied:

- a complete species occurrence list of the site,
- publications based on work at the TGB Osborn Reserve until 2025,
- location maps (as embedded in this document), and
- a georeference file for many of the measurement sites.

For access to original field records and photographs contact the School of Biological Sciences at Adelaide University and at the University Archives. Acknowledgement is due to all the students, staff and researchers who have collected data at the site since its establishment, to those who have entered the data, especially Dr Sinclair, and to the support of funders and interested parties.

References

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Appendix A

Species recorded at the Reserve from all measurements until 2014.

<i>Abutilon</i> sp.	<i>Erodium botrys</i> (Cav.) Bertol.	<i>Omphalolappula concava</i> (F.Muell.) Brand
<i>Acacia aneura</i> F.Muell. ex Benth.	<i>Erodium cicutarium</i> (L.) L'Hér.	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.
<i>Acacia burkittii</i> F.Muell. ex Benth.	<i>Erodium cygnorum</i> Nees	<i>Pittosporum phylliraeoides</i> DC.
<i>Alectryon oleifolius</i> (Desf.) S.T.Reynolds	<i>Erodium</i> sp.	<i>Plagiobothrys</i> sp.
<i>Atriplex acutibractea</i> R.H.Anderson	<i>Eucalyptus microtheca</i> F.Muell.	<i>Ptilotus obovatus</i> (Gaudich.) F.Muell.
<i>Atriplex angulata</i> Benth.	<i>Eucalyptus socialis</i> F.Muell. ex Miq.	<i>Rhagodia</i> sp.
<i>Atriplex eardleyae</i> Aellen	<i>Euphorbia drummondii</i> Boiss.	<i>Rhagodia spinescens</i> R. Br.
<i>Atriplex</i> sp.	<i>Euphorbia</i> sp.	<i>Rhagodia ulicina</i> (Gand.) Paul G.Wilson
<i>Atriplex spongiosa</i> F.Muell.	<i>Exocarpos aphyllus</i> R.Br.	<i>Rhodanthe moschata</i> (A.Cunn. ex DC.) Paul G.Wilson
<i>Atriplex stipitata</i> Benth.	<i>Geococcus</i> sp.	<i>Rhodanthe</i> sp.
<i>Atriplex vesicaria</i> Heward ex Benth.	<i>Gnephosis tenuissima</i> Cass.	<i>Riccia</i> sp.
<i>Austrostipa nitida</i> (Summerh. & C.E.Hubb.) S.W.L.Jacobs & J.Everett	<i>Goodenia</i> sp.	<i>Roepera ammophila</i> (F.Muell.) Beier & Thulin
<i>Austrostipa scabra</i> (Lindl.) S.W.L.Jacobs & J.Everett	<i>Helichrysum</i> sp.	<i>Roepera aurantiaca</i> Lindl.
<i>Austrostipa</i> sp.	<i>Heliotropium</i> sp.	<i>Roepera billardierei</i> (DC.) G.Don
<i>Blennodia</i> sp.	<i>Isoetopsis graminifolia</i> Turcz.	<i>Roepera iodocarpa</i> (F.Muell.) Beier & Thulin
<i>Boerhavia</i> sp.	<i>Lophocolea</i> (Dumort.) Dumort.	<i>Roepera ovata</i> (Ewart & Jean White) Beier & Thulin
<i>Brachyscome lineariloba</i> (DC.) Druce	<i>Lotus australis</i> Andrews	<i>Roepera prismatotheca</i> (F.Muell.) Beier & Thulin
<i>Bromus rubens</i> L.	<i>Lycium australe</i> F.Muell.	<i>Roepera</i> sp.
<i>Calandrinia</i> sp.	<i>Maireana appressa</i> (Benth.) Paul G.Wilson	<i>Salsola kali</i> L.
<i>Callitris preissii</i> Miq.	<i>Maireana astrotricha</i> (L.A.S.Johnson) Paul G.Wilson	<i>Santalum acuminatum</i> (R.Br.) A.DC.
<i>Calotis hispidula</i> (F.Muell.) F.Muell.	<i>Maireana brevifolia</i> (R.Br.) Paul G.Wilson	<i>Santalum lanceolatum</i> R.Br.
<i>Casuarina pauper</i> F.Muell. ex L.A.S.Johnson	<i>Maireana erioclada</i> (Benth.) Paul G.Wilson	<i>Santalum</i> sp.
<i>Chenopodium gaudichaudianum</i> (Moq.) Paul G.Wilson	<i>Maireana excavata</i> (J.M.Black) Paul G.Wilson	<i>Schismus</i> sp.
<i>Convolvulus erubescens</i> Sims	<i>Maireana georgei</i> (Diels) Paul G.Wilson	<i>Sclerolaena obliquicuspis</i> (R.H.Anderson) Ulbr.
<i>Convolvulus</i> sp.	<i>Maireana pyramidata</i> (Benth.) Paul G.Wilson	<i>Sclerolaena patentiscuspis</i> (R.H.Anderson) Ulbr.
<i>Crassula</i> sp.	<i>Maireana sedifolia</i> (F.Muell.) Paul G.Wilson	<i>Sclerolaena</i> sp.
<i>Cucumis</i> sp.	<i>Maireana</i> sp.	<i>Senecio magnificus</i> F.Muell.
<i>Danthonia</i> sp.	<i>Maireana trichoptera</i> (J.M.Black) Paul G.Wilson	<i>Senna artemisioides</i> subsp. x <i>coriacea</i> (Benth.) Randell
<i>Dissocarpus paradoxus</i> (R.Br.) F.Muell. ex Ulbr.	<i>Maireana triptera</i> (Benth.) Paul G.Wilson	<i>Senna artemisioides</i> subsp. x <i>petiolaris</i> Randell
<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i> subsp. <i>angustissima</i> (DC.) J.G.West	<i>Marsdenia</i> sp.	<i>Senna</i> sp.
<i>Dysphania cristata</i> (F.Muell.) Mosyakin & Clemants	<i>Menkea</i> sp.	<i>Sida corrugata</i> Lindl.
<i>Enchylaena tomentosa</i> R.Br.	<i>Millotia muelleri</i> (Sond.) P.S.Short	<i>Sida</i> sp.
<i>Eremophila longifolia</i> (R.Br.) F.Muell.	<i>Myoporum platycarpum</i> R.Br.	<i>Siloxerus multiflorus</i> Nees
<i>Eremophila scoparia</i> (R.Br.) F.Muell.	<i>Nicotiana</i> sp.	<i>Stenopetalum lineare</i> R.Br. ex DC.
<i>Eremophila sturtii</i> R.Br.	<i>Nitraria billardierei</i> DC.	<i>Templetonia egena</i> (F.Muell.) Benth.
<i>Eriochiton sclerolaenoides</i> (F.Muell.) A.J.Scott	<i>Nitraria</i> sp.	<i>Tetragonia</i> sp.
<i>Erodiophyllum elderi</i> F.Muell.	<i>Olearia pimeleoides</i> (DC.) Benth.	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i> L.

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